

Evaluation of Material Culture in Sangam Literature

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Abstract

The material culture of the ancient Tamil people is found neatly inscribed in Sangam literature. All the information available concealed in this language are being analysed and studied on the platform of science. They identify the culture, depending on the tools and materials of everyday life. As these are created by humans, they are known as artistic creations in anthropology. These artistic features are linked to everyday life. Lot of changes have happened in the food sector as well as in the other sections of life like tools, accessories, habits etc. Despite these changes and transformations, there is scope for a changed and refined style of living. This is also a cultural change which reflects people's awareness over overindulgence in artificial and synthetic fibres and products.

Keywords: Literature, Culture, Materials, Food Items, Rice, Paddy, Tamil People, Kanchi, Puttu, Kozhukkattai, Beverages, Moongilarisi, Tools, Trade, Export, Import, etc.

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Introduction

Inscriptions, palm leaf manuscripts, diaries of travellers, archaeological attempts and literature of Sangam Era are the prime sources to know about the early life of Tamil people. The material culture of the ancient Tamil people is found neatly inscribed in Sangam literature.

Dravidian language has been placed in the layers of the worldwide family. Tamil language has been highly placed and acknowledged as a classical language. All the information available concealed in this language are being analysed and studied on the platform of science, engineering, medicine, environment, media, linguistics, psychology and all. and linked to various sections of knowledge. This study is known as material culture in Sangam literature.

Material Culture

Materials in use are considered the base for material culture. How behavioural patterns and actions are important for life situations, in the same way they are the essence of the same hundreds and thousands of features attached to the same culture. Material entities attached to everyday life are identified with that culture. Hunting tools, agricultural implements,, household things and utensils, wooden materials, ornaments, buildings, food materials, roads, buildings, transport materials, writing tools, media etc. are linked to the everyday life; they are not isolated entities, they identify the culture and life, depending on the tools and materials of everyday life. As these are created by humans, they are known as artistic creations in anthropology. These artistic features are linked to everyday life.

Food Materials

Popular fruits included in the diet of the Sangam Era people were mangoes, jack fruit, pomegranate and plantains. Greens, vegetables, spinach, fruits and seeds are other food items consumed by the early inhabitants of Tamilagam. Nutrients like vitamins, iron, calcium and manganese are available in these food items, by which the hill tribes can build up strength and valour. Tubers, roots and lentils provide natural food, and all the nutrients available from these natural foods help to identify and build up the benefits of these foods.

Sugar cane syrup and honey were used to sweeten the dishes. There was salt production in coastal areas. The method of cooking was varied according to the mode of preparation, which are boiling, steaming, frying. Or roasting. Roasting in grills is a popular mode of preparation in vogue during the Sangam Era, mostly in villages. When Tamil people learnt to extract oil from seeds like gingelly, ground nut, coconut etc. They started to use frying mode as a mode of cooking.

Sangam Era Food Habits

Food habits of the Sangam Age was rich in both vegetarian and non-vegetarian items. With millets and rice as staples. The various vegetables the people of the Sangam Age consumed were brinjal, drumstick, gourd varieties, greens, etc. A wide variety of millets were in use then, Millets are known to contain lot of nutrients like iron, calcium and vitamins, which are required for a healthy physique, and these people had knowledge of the same. They made expansive use of the same. which helped them to have a long and healthy life. The millets known to be use those days were:

1. Finger Millet - Kezhvarahu, Koovarahu in Tamil and Ragi in Hindi
2. Pearl Millet - Kampu in Tamil and Bajra in Hindi
3. Fox Tail Millet - Thinai
4. Sorghum - Cholam in Tamil, Jowar in Hindi
5. Barnyard Millet - Kuthiraivali
6. Little Millet - Samai
7. Kodo Millet - Varahu
8. Proso Millet - Pani Varahu
9. Brown Top Millet - Pala pul

Paddy and Rice

Sangam literature speaks of the different varieties of paddy grown and developed in ancient Tamilagam. Chen Nel (red rice), Venn Nel (white rice) mentioned in Aham, 24.16, Puram 33.5, Aham 24.16, Kurum 250 1,12, 12.14 etc. Javane Nel is (Natrinal 373, , Kurum 10.1). Thorai Nel (Madurai, 286.8, Malai 120.1) Kula Nel (Nattrinal. 5.1-2), Doppil Nel (Perum.130:1) are crops cultivated in all the five lands of ancient Tamilagam . Chen Nel is the rice variety regularly used in homes. Champa rice was used by the royals and white rice was used at certain occasions.

There are also references to some of the early varieties of rice in use. They are Pirambarisi (Cane rice- Aham 98:9), Aham 393:12), Moongilarisi (Bamboo rice - 62.4:15), Pullarisi (Grass rice - Aham 377.2). In the modernised agriculture, there are references to mixed crops. During the Sangam Era, they cultivated Thinai (Fox Tail Millet) along with paddy (Puram 199:15-17). Different millet varieties were in vogue in the world of Sangam Era.

Rice obtained after removing the husk from paddy is the major staple food of the Tamil people during the Sangam Era. .As is well known, people all over the world enjoy eating different food preparations made out of rice.

Tamil people of lore ate rice with different other preparations like curry, pulses, vegetables

etc. Rice used to be cooked in different combinations, Eg. Paal Rice (Mil Rice), Nei Choru (Ghee Rice), Oon Choru (Meat Rice) etc. Other varied preparations of rice are Tomato rice, Lemon Rice, Tamarind Rice, Sambar Rice, Curd Rice, etc. Paal Choru is fed to small children and the aged (Puram.382). Mothers feed their little children by pointing to the moon.

Tamil people used to gather after dusk in open air under the skies and enjoy consuming the different varieties of food preparations they have made. Koottan Choru which is a mixture of rice, pulses and vegetables is a special dish during such occasions. In modern terms this is known as 'Moonlight Donner'.

The bamboo (Moongil) blossoms and yields paddy when food materials are in scarce during drought times. During such times, people collect paddy available from bamboo and cook it to bring out a type of rice preparation. (Malai 121 -1211, Aham 1:13, 167:1, 21611).

Moongil Choru has lot of nutrients in it and it has medicinal properties too. It is curative for ailments like fever, head ache, stomach troubles, eye infections etc. When it is ground and applied over the belly, it has the effect to heal stomach pain and stomach disorder. Tamil people ate Moongilarisi with fish. It is written in Perum.94:100.

When the warriors of Sangam Age fell short of food supply, they took Pullarisi (Grass Rice) which is said in Ainkuru Nooru. 42. Pirambarisi was also eaten by some people (Kuram. 96:1). It has less sugar in it and it is recommended for diabetics. It is a health food. It seems the Idayars (shepherds) had a great liking for Varaharisi. (Aham. 193).

Nowadays people have developed a great liking for Pongal, a special rice preparation which is made by adding ghee (butter), spices like cardamom and pepper, cashew nuts and raisins to the mixture of cooked rice and pulses. . During the ancient times, there was a habit of eating porridge made out of rice, Kanchi made of Kambu (Pearl Millet), Cholam (Sorghum) and bamboo rice (Perum. 112-116) is an enhanced and special preparation of Kanchi.

Kanchi (Porridge)

Most Tamils have a liking for taking porridge as food which is made with a combination of rice with different millets. It is a health diet and is very good for ailing patients and those engaged in manual labour. It is prepared by boiling rice and green gram or black gram and peppered with fenugreek (venthayam). Recouping patients are fed Kanchi made with broken rice. Post delivery women are recommended to consume Kanchi made with rice and ban leaves (Murungai). Different types of Kanchi are prepared with the combination of rice with Tur dal, Rongi (Perum Payaru), horse gram (Kollu) or gingelly seeds (Ellu). Also different chutney varieties are prepared to go with these Kanchi preparations, eg. Idi Chammanthi, Dhania Chutney, Coconut Chutney or Thuvaiyal, Pickle, etc. Also dry fish (karuvadu) is a preferred item to eat with Kanchi. Palankanchi is prepared by adding water to the rice cooked in the morning and consumed in the evening, with curd, thuvaiyal or pickle. There are some delicious food preparations made out of roots, tubers, grasses and lentils.

Puttu and Kozhukkattai

'Puttu' is a popular food item eaten by the Tamils. It is made out of roasted rice flour. Thiruvilayadal Puranam speaks of an instance when the god carried earth soil, yearning to have 'Puttu'. Puttu is made by soaking raw rice and then pounding or grinding it, which is then roasted. Puttu is prepared by steaming the roasted rice flour mixed in water and arranging in a tube like vessel (kuzhal) between layers of coconut in a Puttu kudam over a pot with boiling water. In the olden days the puttu vessels were earthenware, but now metal pots and tubes have taken the place of earthenware pots. A slide with holes is placed at the bottom of the puttu kuzhal to let the steam

pass through up. Puttu is eaten with plantain, boiled green gram and papad, with a dash of sugar or jaggery, or even honey.

Kozhukkattai is another delicacy made from rice flour. Karuppukatti(paqlmyra) or jiggery (sugar cane) is mixed with rice flour and added with coconut and spiced with cardamom and dry ginger (Chukku). This mixture is folded in plantain leaves and then steamed over a the idli tray, to get the delicious kozhukkattai. Roasted and ground green gram added to this mixture enhances the taste of this item. Jack tree leaves, Therali leaves, Cheelanthi leaves (Poovarasu) are other substitutes for plantain leaves.

Kozhukkattai is a special dish prepared and enjoyed during the Thirukarthigai festival (Madurai. 623-625). Modagam is a variation of kozhukkattai prepared during the time Vinayaga Chathurthi. (Madurai .626 - 730)..Coconut gratings are mixed with jaggery or sugar and then this mixture is folded inside the rice flour mix and it is steamed over an idli tray to get delicious Modagam.

Material Culture

In the olden days, the paddy got after harvest was brought home after treatment and used in different food preparations. In addition to using rice as a staple food, rice has many applications. Raw rice is pounded or ground to make different palagarams (snacks).. Rice is made to go through various processes for making puttu, dosai and idli. For boiling rice as a staple food, normally par-boiled rice is used in homes.

These processes have gone through various changes and nowadays rice is sent to the mills for grinding or pounding, which then is roasted in the mills itself and packed for sale in the open market. Thus puttu mavu (flour) is made available to the common man without he undergoing the many laborious processes. Even idli and dosa batter is made available, ground at homes and served to people in shops. It is serving as a cottage industry. These details show how Tamil culture is going through different steps and stages and how culture is getting linked to food habits.

It is obvious to notice how human life is undergoing changes and transformations which are taking place in the food sector too. Earlier humans collected their food products in the forests. Later they went for hunting to get their food needs. And they ate the meat of the hunted animals. They used different tools for hunting animals, like point arrow, spear, sword, dagger etc. They developed the taste for eating the hunted animals like rabbits, deer, varaiyadu (Nilgiri Tahr), bullocks, etc. They even caught fish from ponds and lakes and cooked them over grills, rubbed with salt and spices. Those who lived along the coastal region could catch fish from the sea, and they have learned to catch fish in kattumaram (catamaran) too. They could even go diving into the deep sea and collect crabs and mussels. Those who lived in the plains started eating the meat of goat, sheep, ox and fowls. Those who lived in hilly areas ate the meat of wild boar, bullocks, porcupine, blue cow (Milavu), mountain squirrel, wild duck etc.

The meat of some of these animals has the healing effect to cure certain diseases. For example and fox meat is known to cures scabbies. Mountain squirrel cures tuberculosis, Meat of wild cat, mongoose, and even some snakes like python are consumed by the hill side people. Thinai (Fox tail millet) and Samai (Little Millet) are recommended to relieve snake poison. Meat of different animals are salted and preserved for later consumption or salted and preserved in earthenware pots.

Beverages

Tea and coffee are the most sought after beverages. for common consumption. They are consumed in the mornings and the evenings. Tea is sweetened with palmyra jaggery or sugar cane jaggery and added spices like ginger or cardamom or jeera. (caraway seeds) or Tulasi (bay leaves). Most of the hill side people take tea without adding sugar or milk, as they prefer green tea.

Tools in Use during Sangam Age

Blacksmithy was highly advanced during Sangam era, to produce agriculture implements like plough and also domestic tools and war weapons. Brick structures, spinning wheel and rock-hewn beds for ascetics have also been found in excavations, providing evidences for the existence of different economic activities and settlement patterns.

Spear, Arrow heads, Swords and Daggers, were the most common implements used for hunting. Pointed stones such as scrapers and points were also used to aim at the hunted prey by the hunter-gatherer communities in the hilly and dry land regions. The prevalence and material of the tools (stone versus iron) depended on the specific region, the availability of raw materials. and the period within the Sangam Age.

Archaeological excavations indicate the use of the following tools: Specific hunting tools known are:

- | | | |
|-----------------------|---|--|
| Arrow heads | - | often made of iron, used with bows for hunting game |
| Spears and spearheads | - | The spear was a significant cultural symbol, especially associated with the god of hunting and war, Murugan. |
| Swords and daggers | - | These were used for both hunting and warfare (made of iron) |
| Stone tools | - | In the eco-regions like Kurinji (hilly tracts) people used different types of stone tools like scrapers, flakes and points, often with bone or wooden handles. |
| Bone tools | - | Sharply pin-pointed bone top tools, used for hunting or procuring animal hides |
| Traps and Snares | - | also in use |

Hunting involved various methods. People in the hilly and forest region (Mullai) were primarily hunters and gatherers. While those in the agricultural lands (Marutham) focused more on farming. Hunting tools and agricultural implements excavated from graves indicate hunting and agricultural practices prevalent during the Sangam Age.

Sangam Literature

Sangam literature is a major source for giving details of Sangam Age. They are Tolkappiam, Ettuthogai, Pathupattu and Pathinenkizhkanakku. Tolkappiam authored by Tolkappiar is the earliest of Tamil literary work. The two epics of Sangam Age are Silapathigaram and Manimegalai.

Tamil literature speaks of the different export items sent to different countries in ancient Tamilagam. All these materials have emerged in the Sangam literature as a cultural remnant of the people of the land.

Inscriptions and Coinage

Tamil Brahmi inscriptions provide existence of a script used for writing.

Local coins from rulers like the Cheras, Cholas and the Pandyas are found along with the coins of Roman origin. Material culture during the Sangam Age included a variety of artefacts found in archaeological sites which are tools, ceramics and gold jewellery.

Textile industry flourished with the production of cotton and silk fabrics. Evidences for a dyeing industry, in addition to the weaving industry, was also found at Keezhadi excavations.

Trade during Sangam Age

Trade with neighbouring and Far East and West countries flourished during Sangam Age. There was bursting trade during Sangam period, both domestically and internationally. The period also

saw extensive trade with export of cotton, spices, ivory and import of horses and wine. Import and Export materials of Sangam Age are:

Cotton and spices namely pepper, ginger (chukku), cardamom, cinnamon and turmeric were the major export item from Tamilagam.

Import items of ancient Tamilagam were pearls, precious stones, gold, artefacts made of ivory, along with horses and sweets. Textiles were also handled during the trade.

Transformation in Material Culture

In the olden days, wet grinding of rice was done in Aattu kal and dry grinding is done by pounding in Ural and Ulakkai.(mortar and pestle). Kitchen condiments were ground over a stone named 'Ammi and Kuzhavi'. Due to the invention of mixers and grinders functioning with the power of electricity, kitchen work has become easier and less messy, with the effect the stone grinders and pounders have been pushed to the corner. People have become comfort loving and less tasking has become the way of life. These things reflect the life style of the people which in turn is carried over to the culture part of life.

Earlier people were using boxes and containers like muram and petti, made of palmyra fibre or ribs. They came to be considered old fashioned lately. But in the modern age these materials have been replaced by metal or plastic ones, which is considered more durable and convenient, and even modern. However, there is an awareness happening for using products made of natural fibres and in the post modern days, non-government organisations are coming up with the proposals to make the best use of natural fibre products. It is meant to encourage cottage industries. People are slowly shifting to this way of life, as they fear certain disease like cancer attacking them when exposed to high use of plastics and chemical items. It is a welcome change and there is scope for a changed and refined style of living. This is also a cultural change which reflects people's awareness over indulgence in synthetic fibres and products. In all these we see natural products as best for use and consumption.

Pandamatu Murai (exchange of wealth or materials) is giving one product in exchange of another product. Only high valued products were purchased by paying cash. Everyday requirements like rice, pulses, salt, milk, curd, fish, meat etc. Were dealt with this type of exchange mode. This reflects the material culture prevalent during the Sangam Age.

Conclusion

The era's material culture reflects its economy, which was mainly based on agriculture.

The sociology of the people of Sangam Era can be ascertained through Sangam literature. All the products people use in their day-to-day lives are all meant to express material culture. These products can be called as 'every day commodities'. Hence it can be concluded that the material culture of the sangam Era has been passed on to the present era, although with slight changes in its face value.

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